

Illustrative Review on Rotavirus Vaccines

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ABSTRACT

Rotavirus (RV) is a disease that is extremely spreadable in children whose age ranges between 3–5 years. Rotavirus vaccination (RVV) is an effective method for combating the diarrhoea disease as rotavirus is the leading cause of diarrhoea worldwide. For fulfilling the aim of reducing the burden of RV caused in children under 5 years for diarrhoea mortality. World Health Organization (WHO) recommends introducing RVVs worldwide. Globally three RVVs are licensed for local use; two monovalent vaccines Rotarix, and Rotavac and a pentavalent vaccine RotaTeq. Safety and efficacy of these vaccines have been proved, however, they require cold-chain storage at or below 20 to 80°C before use. In this article, a detailed profile of Rotarix vaccine is being emphasized. Rotavirus Vaccines are in high demand for introduction by many low-income countries, but limitations such as price, poor supply and insufficient cold-chain capacity at distant delivery points, have restricted their introduction.

KEYWORDS: Rotavirus, Rotavirus vaccination (RVV), Rotarix

How to cite this paper: A. A Bhosale | Dr. V. U Barge "Illustrative Review on Rotavirus Vaccines" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-4 | Issue-1, December 2019, pp.383-388, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd29552.pdf>

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1. INTRODUCTION

Major cause of severe gastroenteritis among young children is rotavirus. It is a major cause of under-5-year-old mortality in developing countries, responsible for up to 20% of all childhood deaths in nations with high diarrhoeal disease burden. First rotavirus infections normally occur between 6-9 months of age, and 80% occur among infants <1-year-old in developing countries. Every year, rotavirus causes >500,000 deaths worldwide among infants and very young children, approximately 90% of these deaths occurring in Africa and Asia itself. Around the world, about 40% of all paediatric hospitalizations for diarrhoea are due to rotavirus infections.

Epidemiology Studies

Each year, rotavirus gastroenteritis is estimated to cause almost 527,000 (475,000-580,000) deaths worldwide among children ranging between <5 years of age and worldwide, >2 million children are hospitalized each year for sufferings caused due to rotavirus. Most incidences of severe rotavirus disease occur in high-mortality countries.

Through the employment of various police surveillance methods techniques, the 2001-2008 report indicated a median rotavirus hospitalization detection rate of 34% in the America, 40% in both Europe and the Eastern Mediterranean, 41% in Africa, and 45% in South East Asia and the Western Pacific. These high proportions are far greater than two previous estimates of rotavirus-

attributable hospitalizations in international scenario. Previously median rotavirus detection rate of 22% was reported in one review of studies that had been published during the years 1986-1999, and another review from 1990-2004 reported that a median of 29% of diarrhoeal hospitalizations were due to the cause of rotavirus.

VIROLOGICAL REVIEW

Rotaviruses are double-stranded (ds) RNA viruses: genus Rotavirus, family Reoviridae. Each of the 11 dsRNA segments, contained within the core of a triple-layered viral particle, encodes one or more viral proteins. Rotavirus A, which causes most human disease, is genetically diverse in each of its 11 genome segments (called genotypes), and a nucleotide sequence-based, complete genome classification system is used. Rotaviruses were discovered in the 1960s in animals.

- The virus was 1st delineated in humans when it had been found by microscopy in duodenal biopsies from children with acute gastroenteritis.
- Rotaviruses are 70-nm icosahedral viruses. They belong to the family Reoviridae.
- Seven reovirus serogroups (serogroups A to G) are represented.
- Most human pathogens belong to groups A, B, and C.
- The virus comprises of 3 smaller molecular weight shells, an outer capsid, an inner capsid, and an internal core, that surround the 11 segments of double-stranded RNA (Fig. 1).

1. Rotavirus vaccines are designed to protect against disease caused by the most prevalent strain types; globally,
 - G1P [8],
 - G2P [4],
 - G3P [8],
 - G4P [8],
 - G9P [8] and
 - G12 in combination with P [6] or P [8] account for over 90% of the genotypes that infect humans

For the foremost part, each gene segment codes for a single protein.

When mixed infection with over one animal virus strain tends to preside, the sequence segments from the parental viruses may reassort with a great impact, manufacturing reassortant of mixed parentage, a supply of agent diversity.

PROTECTION THROUGH NATURAL METHODS AND IMMUNOGENETICITY

Rotavirus infections are more likely to be severe in children 3 to 24 months older than in younger infants or older kids and adults.

Longitudinal studies incontestable that naturally non-genetic reovirus infections provide protection against rotavirus unease upon reinfection which protection is greatest against prime severe disease outcomes.

Although children are often infected with rotavirus many times during their lives, initial infection after 3 months of age is most likely to cause severe diarrhoea and dehydration.

Rotavirus vaccines induce serum IgA, which has been identified as a potential correlate of protection. The presence of maternal antibody appears to provide protection against rotavirus to the youngest infants (up to 3 months of age). However, high levels of rotavirus antibody and non-antibody components of breast milk can affect the infant immune response to rotavirus vaccines. These effects are most pronounced in infants from low- and middle-income countries where rotavirus infection is most prevalent. It is unlikely that withholding breast feeding improves the vaccine response in these high exposure situations.

After premeditative natural infection, infants and young children are protected against subsequent symptomatic

disease regardless of whether first infection was symptomatic or asymptomatic.

Humoral immunity is believed to play an important role in protection.

Studies of monkeys have demonstrated that the passive transfer of serum antibodies can give protection against infection.

Studies have additionally incontestable that the first infection with reovirus elicits a predominantly homotypic, serum-neutralizing antibody response to the virus, and subsequent infections elicit a broader, heterotypic response.

Review proof from string of studies of humans, including challenge experiments with adult volunteers, longitudinal studies of rotavirus infection in young children, and clinical trials of animal and animal-human reassortant rotavirus vaccines in infants, suggests that blood serum antibodies, if present at critical levels, are either protective themselves or an important and powerful correlate of protection against rotavirus disease, even though other host effectors may play an important role as well VP6 is the immunodominant substance within the protein response to human rotavirus infection.

Serum IgA (IgA) or immunoglobulin G antibodies against VP6 substance tested by super molecule immunochemical assay are thought to be an indicator of RVV immunity when infection and vaccination. A high level of blood serum immune globulin protein correlates with clinical protection against reovirus stomach flu.

Neutralizing antibodies against VP7 and VP4 antigens clearly play a role in protection after natural rotavirus infection, but their role in rotavirus vaccine-induced immunity is less clear.

The current live oral reovirus vaccines rely on the concept that immunity to the rotavirus surface antigens is essential is crucial} or important for vaccine-induced protection. However, vaccines that elicit low levels of blood serum antibodies are effective in field trials.

VACCINE BASED ON HUMAN ROTAVIRUS

ROTARIX

DESCRIPTION

ROTARIX (human animal virus, live, attenuated, oral vaccine) may be a suspension conferred in monodose oral applicators or monodose tubes for oral administration. There is an inclusion of an antacid component for protection of the vaccine during passage through the stomach and for the purpose of prevention of its inactivation due to presence of acidic condition.

INDICATIONS AND CLINICAL USE

ROTARIX is indicated for active immunization of infants from the age of 6 weeks for the prevention of gastroenteritis caused by circulating rotavirus strains. Results obtained from the clinical trials are suggestive of the fact that the vaccine's efficacy may change according to the type of rotavirus causing the infection.

ROTARIX should not be administered in:

- Infants experiencing hypersensitivity to this drug or to any of the ingredients present in the formulation or any container/closure components.
- Previous history of hypersensitivity by infants on administration of rotavirus vaccines. and infants with uncorrected congenital malformation of the gastrointestinal tract that would incline for intussusception.
- Cases of Severe Combined Immunodeficiency (SCID) disorder (see ADVERSE REACTIONS).
- Infants having a history of intussusception.

WARNINGS AND PRECAUTIONS

Review of medical history should be performed prior to vaccination.

ROTARIX administration should be postponed in infants suffering from acute severe febrile illness.

No safety or efficacy knowledge are obtainable for the administration of ROTARIX to:

- individuals WHO have received an intravenous or blood product, including immunoglobulins, within 42 days.

No effectuality information is available for the administration of ROTARIX to:

- Immunocompromised patients like subjects with malignancies receiving immunosuppressive therapies or who are immunocompromised in other ways.

The administration of ROTARIX should be postponed in infants suffering from diarrhoea or vomiting.

Healthcare providers should include and involve follow-up on any symptoms indicative of intussusception (severe abdominal pain, persistent vomiting, bloody stools, and/or high fever) as a precautionary measure. In case of such symptoms, parents/guardians should be advised to report such incidences.

Excretion of the vaccine virus in the stools is believed to occur after vaccination and it lasts for about 10 days on average with peak excretion occurring around the 7th day. Viral antigen particles detected by ELISA were found in 50% (at day 7) of stools after the first dose and 17.4% (at day 3) and 4% (at day 7) of stools after the second dose.

When these stools were tested for the presence of live immunizing agent strain, only 17 November were positive.

Cases of transmission of excreted vaccine virus to seronegative contacts of vaccines have been observed in clinical trials without causing any clinical symptoms. Individuals with immunodeficient close contacts, such as individuals with various kind of malignancies and tumours, or who are otherwise compromised immunologically or receiving immunosuppressive therapy should administer ROTARIX with utmost care and caution. Contacts of recent vaccines should maintain proper and careful hygiene (including washing their hands) while changing children's diapers.

As with any vaccine, a protective immune response may not be elicited in all vaccines.

ROTARIX does not defend against gastroenteritis due to various pathogens than rotavirus.

No data are out there on the utilization of ROTARIX for post-exposure prevention.

UNDER NO CIRCUMSTANCES SHOULD ROTARIX BE INJECTED

Gastrointestinal

There is not any resourceful evidence on the protection and efficacy of ROTARIX in infants with epithelial duct illnesses.

ROTARIX should be administered with caution in infants when withholding the vaccine entails a greater risk, and in such cases, the opinion of the physician should be taken into consideration.

Immune

In some clinical trials, ROTARIX was not administered to infants who known to have any household members with immunodeficiency. There is a considerable risk that the live virus vaccine can be transmitted to non-vaccinate contacts. Thus, ROTARIX should be administered with alertness and caution by the individuals known to have immunodeficient close contacts such as:

- Individuals with malignancies or who immunocompromisable; or
- Individuals undergoing immunosuppressive therapy.

The health care provider should assess the potential risks and benefits of administering ROTARIX to infants known to have immunodeficient close contacts.

Asymptomatic and mildly symptomatic HIV infections are not quite believed to be expected to affect the safety and efficacy of ROTARIX vaccine.

Administration of ROTARIX in immunosuppressed infants, including infants on immunosuppressive therapy, should be based on careful consideration of potential benefits and risks.

Sensitivity/Resistance

1073 mg of sucrose is present as an excipient. This specified amount is considerably low to cause undesirable effects in patients with rare hereditary issues such as fructose intolerance, glucose-galactose malabsorption or sucrase-isomaltose insufficiency.

Special Populations Breastfeeding Infants: evidence from some clinical trials with ROTARIX implies that breastfeeding does not effectively scale back the protection against rotavirus inflammatory disease due to ROTARIX.

Therefore, breastfeeding may be continued during the vaccination time period.

Post-Marketing Adverse Drug Reactions

Below mentioned effects have been reported during post-approval use of ROTARIX spontaneously. But these

effects were reported voluntarily from a population of a disproportionate size, it is not possible to reliably estimate their frequency or to establish a causal relationship to vaccine exposure.

Gastrointestinal disorders: Haematochezia, Gastroenteritis with vaccine viral shedding in infants with Severe Combined Immunodeficiency (SCID) disorder.

Infections: Kawasaki disease

DRUG INTERACTIONS

Use with other vaccines ROTARIX can be given in association with any of the following monovalent or combination vaccines:

1. Diphtheria tetanus-whole cell pertussis vaccine (DTPw) and Diphtheria-tetanus-acellular pertussis vaccine (DTPa)
2. Haemophilus influenzae type b vaccine (Hib)
3. Inactivated polio vaccine (IPV), hepatitis B vaccine (HBV)
4. Pneumococcal conjugate vaccine
5. Meningococcal serogroup C conjugate vaccine.

Clinical studies show that the immune responses to and the safety profiles of the administered vaccines were not affected.

DOSAGE AND ADMINISTRATION

Dosing regimens

- ROTARIX is for oral use solely.
- UNDER NO CIRCUMSTANCES SHOULD ROTARIX BE INJECTED.

Recommended Dose and Dosage Adjustment

Vaccination duration/course consists of two doses. The first dose can be administered from the age of 6 weeks.

There should be AN interval of a minimum of 4 weeks between doses.

ROTARIX may be given to preterm infants considering the same vaccination course. The administration of the 2 doses should be completed by the age of 24 weeks. In particular circumstances, if the vaccine is given at an earlier age, and that the second dose is given within the shortest interval of 4 weeks, an immune response induced may be of lower value.

Firm recommendation is suggested that infants who receive a first dose of ROTARIX complete the 2-dose regimen with ROTARIX.

ACTION AND CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY

Infection occurring due to rotavirus is the prime cause of severe acute gastroenteritis in infants and young children around the world. Transmission of rotavirus occurs mainly by the fecal-oral route, through close contact from person-to-person, and through fomites. Ingested virus particles infect the cells in the villi of the small intestine, mainly leading to cause villous atrophy. Characteristic clinical features include diarrhoea, vomiting, fever and abdominal discomfort, which often leads to fatal dehydration and subsequent illness.

Rotavirus infection primarily affects 95% of children by the age of 3 to 5 years throughout the world.

Rotavirus infections is highest in kids between 6 and 24 months older.

Primary infection after 3 months of age usually causes the most severe disease. Subsequent infections are possible but it does not cause much stronger symptoms. In the US and, in Canada (based upon limited data), six rotavirus serotypes (P1A [8]G1, P1B [4]G2, P1A [8]G3, P1A [8]G4, P1A [8]G9, and P2A [6]G9) cause the majority of disease. These strains are generally designated by their G serotype specificity (serotypes G1-4 and G9). Approximately 55-65% of all rotavirus gastroenteritis in 2 Canadian studies were caused by G1 serotype

FUTURE CHALLENGES

Post marketing surveillance studies to monitor the impact of vaccine on circulating viral strains recovered from stool samples will be important to screen for possible vaccine selection pressure and strain replacement. Studies to measure the extent of cross-protection against different rotavirus serotypes, including serotype G9, which is becoming increasingly important across Asia and Africa, and G8, which is gaining prevalence in components of Africa, will also need to be carried out to ensure that the vaccine protects children in the developing world, where those strains are prevalent.

The implementation of reovirus protection programs would force scientists and health officers to figure effectively with the media to identify that the general public is familiar regarding each the risks and benefits of the new reovirus vaccines, particularly since the media may be the public's principal source of such information. A balanced portrayal of these risks and benefits can help avert abrupt shifts in media and public reactions that can undermine the success of vaccination programs.

Accurate info on vaccine risks and edges can type the inspiration of the dialogue that has got to take place between clinicians, health authorities, legislators, and the public to maintain public trust in rotavirus immunization. The development and introduction of rotavirus vaccines for children in the resource-poor countries of the world have been given high priority by the WHO.

Vaccine efficaciousness, which has already been incontestable in youngsters in industrialised and middle-income countries, must be established in resource-poor countries in African continent and Asia.

The availability of these vaccines can depend on distribution, including the need for a cold chain.

The WHO's Initiative for Vaccine Research intends to provide funding for the development of liquid or dry powder formulations of rotavirus vaccines to facilitate the development of rotavirus vaccines

that are logistically easy to administer in resource-poor countries, occupy minimal space in the cold chain, may be stored outside of the cold chain for reasonable time

periods without a loss of activity, and are compatible with multidose vial formats.

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